

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

LYUBOMYR ROMANKIV: THE STATE SHOULD BE BUILT BY STRONG YOUNG PEOPLE

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Abstract

The study examines the life and work of the world-renowned Ukrainian scientist Lubomyr Romankiv. Having gained recognition and having dual citizenship, Canadian and American, the scientist emphasised that he lived in Ukraine. Therefore, the focus is on his attitude to Ukrainianness, his homeland, and political processes in the Ukrainian SSR and modern Ukraine through the prism of his life experience. Lubomyr's worldview was formed overseas, but L. Romankiv has remained a passionate patriot of Ukraine all his life, although he is convinced that his father would have been shot in 1944 for his active pro-Ukrainian position, and he himself would have been exiled to Siberia. At the same time, he sees the consequences of Soviet domination in modern Ukraine, as some politicians with an anti-Ukrainian stance have retained the Soviet mentality to some extent, as they have been engaged in personal enrichment instead of building the state, while unique scientific programmes have been declining and young people are forced to look for work abroad. That is why the world-famous Ukrainian devoted a significant part of his activities to the Plast organization, relying on young people.

Keywords: Diaspora, Lubomyr Romankiv, scientist, IT sector, Plast, Ukrainian people.

Ukrainians abroad constitute one of the largest communities in the world and are roughly equal to the current population of Ukraine (although data on the number of Ukrainians abroad vary considerably: by 2022, there were between 7 and 20 million, and since 2022, another 2.4 million to 6.24 million, or even 8 million, have left). The diaspora has consistently supported Ukraine by providing extensive financial and humanitarian aid, and since the period of Russian aggression, military aid. The diaspora also lobbies for Ukraine's interests, influencing the governments of its countries of residence. For example, thanks to its work, the US Senate Foreign Relations Committee passed the bill «Protecting American Security from Kremlin Aggression Act» in 2019, and Canada became one of the first countries to provide assistance to Ukraine after 2014, when hostilities began in eastern Ukraine. The diaspora's activity in the international arena also led to the fact that in 2022 a number of countries were ready to provide military and economic support [4, p.116]. The full-scale invasion further united the diaspora. Volunteer movements were organized, humanitarian, financial and military aid was collected, picketing of Russian embassies began, and Ukrainians in their countries of residence told the truth about the invasion on television, radio and in the local press. Countering Russian propaganda abroad, which is especially dangerous in a hybrid war, has also become an important area of diaspora activity.

A significant role in the positive perception of Ukraine by the international community is played by internationally recognized Ukrainians. For example, on 27 November 1991, with the assistance of Bush's press secretary, Roman Popadiuk, the political leadership of the Ukrainian diaspora, led by the head of the Ukrainian Congress Committee of America, A. Lozynskyj, met

with the US president, who initially had a negative attitude to the idea of Ukraine's independence. However, the diaspora managed to pass a resolution in both houses of Congress demanding that G.Bush recognise the independence of the Ukrainian state [13], and at a personal meeting he promised to do so immediately after the referendum. We can also recall the events of 2022, when the sex symbol of the 1950s and 1960s, French actress and writer of Ukrainian descent Milène Demongeau, drew the attention of her French friends to Ukraine: Pierre Richard, Alain Delon, Jean-Paul Belmondo.

Thanks to the activities of such personalities, Ukrainian studies are developing around the world, and Ukraine is supported, assisted, and promoted in its Atlantic and European integration. At the same time, Ukrainians do not know enough about the lives and activities of their compatriots abroad. One of the reasons for Ukrainians' lack of interest in this issue is certain mental problems. We are talking about the inferiority complex associated with Russification, as it can cause economic and intellectual dependence, which affects «the perception, assimilation of any information and weakens the energy of thinking» [7, p. 179]. The study and popularization of significant historical events and personalities, as well as the spread of Ukrainian studies, will help to change this situation. It is worth looking at any great nation that is not only proud of its national figures of science and culture, but also promotes their work as much as possible. A similar system should be developed in Ukraine.

One of these prominent figures in the Ukrainian diaspora is Lubomyr Romankiv, who is known as the «godfather» of Apple, and in Japan, thin-film magnetic heads used to be named after him. In fact, when any computer is switched on, seven patented inventions of the prominent Ukrainian immediately start working.

These inventions contributed to the emergence of a new computer era, as they made it possible to create personal computers [12, p.200]. At the same time, having gained international recognition and having dual citizenship, Canadian and American, Lubomyr Romankiv emphasized that he lived in Ukraine, «Ukraine is the most important country for me» [1].

Analysis of the latest research and publications.

The historiography of one of the most talented inventors of our time, Liubomyr Romankiv, can be divided into several parts. The first part includes research by scholars in the technical field. In particular, Hnitetska T.V., Hnitetska H.O. and Varakuta M.O. studied L. Romankiv's contribution to the field of technology and said that «the most precious awards for him» are associated with strengthening the international authority of Ukraine' [3]. In our opinion, the article by O. Polevetska and V. Shenderovskiyi is interesting, given that Professor Shenderovskiyi was personally acquainted with L. Romankiv. In a conversation, the prominent inventor said «that he had an idea to build a small computer that could be carried in a pocket and would be connected to the human brain by an electronic signal» [11, p. 28].

The second group includes essays by historians, geographers, information from Ukrainka and library blogs [12; 10; 8; 14], which not only describe technical inventions and tell about the life of L. Romankiv, but also offer a selection of facts about famous Ukrainian figures who played a major role in the development of national and world science and culture. This criterion may be relevant in the implementation of the Ukraine-centred approach in education [10, p. 85].

The largest group is made up of publications in the media, which not only provide material about the prominent Ukrainian, but also offer the opportunity to watch an interview with him. For example, Forbes magazine contains information about the life and scientific activities of L. Romankiv, who worked for IBM for more than 50 years, patented 67 inventions and wrote more than 150 scientific articles [9].

The publications of the global Ukrainian community - Voice of America and Radio Liberty - describe certain details of the life of the prominent Ukrainian. For example, L. Romankiv told Voice of America that «Apple was founded in the way that Wozniak bought these discs from us and built the first computer, a personal computer, in his garage, and then Jobs, who did not really know the technology, but he was a good salesman, became interested in it, and he started building that Apple company» [6], while Radio Liberty told about the escape of L. Romankiv's family. Romankiv's family's escape «from the Soviet occupation», his work in Plast, and his own vision of the future of Ukraine, which «should be developed by strong young people who have seen the world, learned it and returned» [5]. The Ukrainian media did not ignore Lubomyr Romankiv, in particular, in the publication «Ukrainska Pravda. Zhyttia» we find interesting facts from his personal life, for example, that «he still does not have his own computer at home» [1]. At the same time, despite a large number of publications, there is no separate study on L. Romankiv's contribution to the promotion

of Ukraine in the world and his attitude towards Ukrainians and the Ukrainian government.

Results of the study. Liubomyr Romankiv has 180 scientific discoveries, 68 of which are patented [1], and this includes not only the IT sector but also the zinc mining technology that has been in use for almost 40 years. In 1986, L. Romankiv was awarded the IBM Fellow distinction for his scientific achievements, which has been given to only 331 people over the years of the company's existence. In 1993, the scientist received the highest honors of the US Chemical Society - the Perkin Medal, in 1994 he received the Gold Medal of the US Electrochemical Society, and in 2000 he was recognized as the Inventor of the Year by the Eastern New York Intellectual Property Rights Association. For his outstanding inventions, the scientist has received 13 awards from the IIM and 25 awards for inventions and achievements. In 2012, he was inducted into the U.S. National Hall of Fame, becoming the second Ukrainian after Igor Sikorsky and one of ten inventors (along with Steve Jobs) to receive this honor. Liubomyr Romankiv is listed in the prestigious Who's Who in the Scientific World and Who's Who in America. Some of his ideas were far ahead of their time. For example, in the 1970s, the prominent Ukrainian proposed to build a small computer connected by an electrical signal to the human brain to help memorise information. However, his boss did not even want to sign a patent agreement for this invention, and today Elon Musk's company is working on such a computer and conducting experiments on monkeys by implanting chips in their brains [5].

Of course, L. Romankiv did not start making inventions right away, but he was talented since childhood. Liubomyr was born on 17 April 1931 in Zhovkva, Lviv region. However, in 1944 he left Ukraine with his parents. When Soviet troops were advancing to the West, many Ukrainian families did not want to go to the Soviet «paradise» and were forced to flee. Moreover, L. Romankiv's father was a well-known lawyer and head of Prosvita. Obviously, the Soviet authorities hated any manifestation of national consciousness, and put Lubomyr's father on the «execution list» [11]. «When the Soviet troops came to Zhovkva in the evening, the lists of those who were to be shot the next morning appeared at night. My father was on the list» Lubomyr recalls [5]. The modern Russian authorities use similar methods. Let us recall the lists of Ukrainian patriots that the occupiers had in 2022.

Thus, L. Romankiv's father moved to Uhniv, where the Germans stayed, and the next night he took his family - his wife, daughter, and son Liubomyr. The family first went to Krynica (Poland), then to Bratislava (Slovakia). After the war ended, they ended up in Austria near Salzburg, and from there they moved to a camp for displaced people in Munich. Through the UN, the family moved to Edmonton (Canada), as L. Romankov's great-grandfather had a farm in the province of Alberta. Then he studied in Winnipeg, Toronto, and the University of Alberta (USA).

Despite the fact that Lubomyr left Ukraine at the age of 13 and lived his entire life overseas, he carried his love for his homeland throughout his life. This was

due to his Ukrainian roots, family traditions, studying with Ukrainian teachers, and his work in Plast. Liubomyr Romankiv recalled: «e had a saying in my house: «When you cross this threshold, you have entered our Ukraine. Only Ukrainian is spoken here». In 1946, while living in Berchtesgaden (Germany), L. Romankiv became a member of Plast, and when the family moved to Edmonton (Canada), where he graduated from grade 11 of a Ukrainian Catholic school with three teachers of Ukrainian descent born in Canada [1]. There he became the organiser of the village and initiated the purchase of a Plast house. Later, in Boston (USA), he worked as a youth educator, and in 1965-1977, he was the 2nd Deputy of the Plast Regional Elder and Secretary of the Plast in the USA [11]. «Plast self-organised me and gave me a certain way of thinking, Ukrainian patriotism», emphasises L. Romankiv [5].

However, these events took place overseas, where Lubomyr became a Ukrainian patriot. What happened in Ukraine? A case in Kyiv was illustrative: in 1971, Lubomyr was invited to Moscow University to give a talk. He agreed only on the condition that he receive permission to travel to Kyiv and Lviv. In Moscow, the scholar found out that he was under constant surveillance, and that the possibility of visiting Ukraine would depend on «his behaviour». Since this round-the-clock 'care' by Soviet secret services had no results (no anti-Sovietness or «espionage» was detected), he was invited to give a lecture at Kyiv University. Before the lecture in Kyiv, Lubomyr was asked in which language he would speak: English, Russian, or Ukrainian? The answer was obvious - in Ukrainian. L. Romankiv emphasised that he was a Ukrainian, invited as a Ukrainian, and the inventions were made by a Ukrainian, not, for example, a Canadian or an American». That is why he spoke in his native language. However, the head of the chemical engineering department, Professor Andropov, said: «Call an interpreter, because I don't understand Ukrainian very well» L. Romankiv was shocked that a professor at a Ukrainian university did not understand Ukrainian and asked for a Russian interpreter [1]. He also refused to move to Ukraine, despite numerous offers in the early 1970s, because «I would have had financial constraints and would not have had the opportunities». L. Romankiv is convinced that «if he had stayed in Ukraine, he would have ended up in Siberia or shot» [5].

After returning to the United States, Lubomyr Romankiv continued to develop Ukrainianism as the head of the Plast Mace from 1978 to 1984, which is the executive body of the Plast movement [11]. At work, he was even joked that he had two jobs: one at the IIR during the day, and at Plast in the evening, when the morning in Ukraine came. Later, L. Romankiv became the founder of the Drota Foundation (the «Primary Plast Foundation») and every year since 1991 he visited Ukraine to help the work of Ukrainian Plast members. In particular, he twice took them to scout congresses (in the Netherlands in 1995 and in Chile in 1999). In Ukraine, he was elected Chief Plast member at the Jubilee meeting dedicated to the 85th anniversary of the

Plast oath, which took place on Mount Sokil on 10 August 1997, and in 2003 was re-elected for a new term [11]. During 1997-2007, the Fund provided USD 60 thousand annually to pay for Plast employees [2]. The work in Plast is explained by the position of Liubomyr Romankiv on the importance of raising strong and conscious Ukrainian youth. «...We always consider what unites us Ukrainians and what we need to cherish in order to unite the Ukrainian people...» [11]. «I have both Canadian and American citizenship, but this does not mean that I consider myself an American. I consider myself a Ukrainian. Nothing else!» [8] - emphasised L. Romankiv.

After the declaration of Ukraine's independence, Lubomyr constantly visited his homeland, observing political, economic and scientific processes. He recognised that Ukraine was a leading country in the world in many areas, such as rocketry. It also had its own unique enterprises: «Motor Sich, Yuzhmash, the Mriya aircraft, etc. In particular, when America started building missiles, it turned to Ukraine for help. On the other hand, I saw how the Buran programme began to decline, that «...the president was installing golden toilets. «And for one such toilet, he could have sent one student who would have returned and done some important technical work in Ukraine» [2]. L. Romankiv believed that the government in Ukraine had no idea how to develop science in the country, as he had repeatedly met in America with the best programmers who had studied in Ukraine but were unable to get a good job in their homeland and had to go to work in America.

Conclusions. Thus, Liubomyr Romankiv clearly distinguished between the concepts of Ukraine, Ukrainian youth and the government. On the one hand, we see his boundless love for Ukraine. Lubomyr had a large Ukrainian library that included, among other things, all the works of Shevchenko, Franko, etc., he developed Plast, made a lot of efforts to ensure that the state was built by strong young people who had seen the world, learned about it, and returned. He also saw the consequences of Soviet rule, as he is convinced that his father would have been shot in 1944 for his active pro-Ukrainian position, and he himself would have been exiled to Siberia. To a certain extent, some politicians with an anti-Ukrainian stance have retained the Soviet mentality, as they have been engaged in personal enrichment instead of building the state, while unique scientific programmes have been declining and young people are forced to look for work in a «foreign land». That is why the world-famous Ukrainian devoted a significant part of his activities to the Plast organisation, focusing on young people.

Given the need to develop not only Ukrainian studies, but also the formation of national memory in the context of Russian aggression, including information, the study and promotion of the activities of prominent Ukrainians may be the subject of further research.

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